

Paper for the European Consortium for Political Research (ECPR) 2018 General
Conference, Hamburg, Germany, August, 22nd -25th 2018

Workshop: Political Participation, Political Representation and Voting Advice Applications

Measuring Issue Congruence Between German Parties and Voters

Stefan Marschall¹, Lucas Constantin Wurthmann¹ & Vasiliki Triga²

– Draft-Version –

Abstract

For the relatively stable and predictable German political system, the outcome of the Federal elections of 2017 was a remarkable surprise, with the country's two major political parties noting record losses, the major beneficiary being a relative newcomer to the political scene, the Alternative für Deutschland (AfD) party. This paper traces the trajectory of AfD from a primarily Euro-sceptic and market-friendly party in 2013 to a mainly culturally conservative and anti-immigrant party in 2017. Data from the ParteieNavi2017 Voting Advice Application are then used to attempt to trace the conditions at the individual level of analysis that fostered vote-switching behaviour from the two established mainstream parties (CDU/CSU and SPD) toward AfD. We find neither demographic characteristics nor self-placement of users on the economic Left-Right axis to be a determinant of vote switching to AfD; on the other hand, self-placement on the socio-cultural Liberal-Progressive dimension and policy preferences for anti-immigration and anti-EU integration policies were significant predictors of such voting behaviour.

Introduction

En route to the German Federal elections of 2017, the outcome appeared predictable; the country had returned to steady economic growth, unemployment rates had been kept low and the leader of the incumbent party, A. Merkel, remained popular, reasonably expecting to retain the Chancellorship (see Wiliarty, 2018). Yet the outcome of the elections delivered not only record losses for the two most powerful parties and the largest number of parties in the Bundestag (six) in more than 60 years (Switek 2017: 62) but an unusually long and arduous coalition building process to form a grand coalition government. The 2017 result was commented on as a “political earthquake” (Siri, 2018; p.141), with the potential to transform the political system, although this is more a function of the predictability and expectedness of the German context rather than the uniqueness of the result when seen in comparative manner to other elections internationally, particularly since 2015.

Indeed, the German political system had proven to be remarkably stable and consolidated since the 1960s, by which time the 9 original parties of the post-WW II Bundestag had been absorbed by three parties: the Christian Democrat party (CDU/CSU), the Social Democratic Party (SPD) and the Free Democratic Party (FDP). This particular configuration of power remained stable until 1983 and post-reunification, when the Green party and die Linke (“the Left”) entered the Bundestag. Electoral power during this period was predominately shared by the two larger and mainstream parties (Volksparteien), CDU/CSU and SPD, which cumulatively averaged 82.7% of the vote between 1961 and 2005, after which point their combined vote share dropped to 59.1%, although electoral losses were primarily confined to the centre-left SPD which went from achieving 38.9% vote share on average to 23.1% in the three elections after 2005; CDU, on the other hand, has been more successful than other Christian Democrat parties across Europe in retaining the loyalty of its constituency (Bale & Krouwel, 2013). Given this high concentration of votes, as expected, the two had shared the Chancellorship for the period (48 years for CDU/CSU, 20 for SPD). Neither ever managed a majority, however, necessitating coalition governments, formed for the most part with FDP, a pro-European party advocating economic and social liberalism (Imerfall & Sobisch, 1997), with an exception for an SPD-Greens coalition and four grand coalition governments (CDU-SPD) between 1966 – 1969, 2005-2009 and 2013 – 2017, adding that the current government is a grand coalition one.

The election of 2017

The 2017 election saw the trend of diminishing power for the two Volksparteien that started in the mid-2000s continue, despite an enhanced turnout rate from 2013; the Christian Democrats (CDU/CSU), secured 32.9% of the vote, a loss of 8.6% from 2013, the second worst electoral outcome since the first free election of 1949 and the greatest loss the party ever experienced in a federal election (although this should be seen in light of the remarkably successful outcome of the 2013 election). Similarly, the Social Democrats recorded a loss of 5.2% (20.5% overall vote share), the worst election outcome in their history since World War II.

The two parties together lost 4.7 million votes compared to the 2013 federal election, which translated into gains for the minor parties, six of which managed to cross the Parliament threshold and be represented in the Bundestag. Although minor parties benefited across the board, the electoral gains were not equally distributed, with parties on the left of SPD on the political spectrum, the Greens and die Linke, attracting an additional 0.5 million voters each (gains of 0.5% and 0.6% respectively). The major beneficiaries of the election had been FDP, which increased its vote share by 5.9% (3.1 million more voters) and Alternative für Deutschland (AfD) which attracted about 5.9 million voters (12.6% of the electorate), 3.8 million more votes than in 2013, a swing of 7.9%.

Indeed the rise of AfD was perhaps the most notable feature of the 2017 election, as not only was becoming the third most successful party an extraordinary feat for an organization founded only 4 years earlier, it was also the best result of any party newly entering the Bundestag since 1949 (Goerres, Spies & Kumlin, 2018). Moreover, it was also the first time since 1957 that a party, explicitly positioning itself to the right of the Christian Democrats on the political spectrum succeeded to enter the Bundestag (Dilling 2018: 84), disproving the aphorism of former party leader, Franz-Josef Strauß (CSU), that “there cannot be a democratically legitimized party to the right of the CSU”.

The failure of “radical” Right-wing parties in Germany

Strauß’s confidence in excluding this possibility was, on one hand, not unwarranted since until 2017, the most successful such attempt took place in the 1960s when the National-Democratic Party of Germany obtained 4.3% of the national vote, falling short of the 5% threshold. On the other hand, a number of radical right-wing parties have seen success at the local and state (Länder) levels (see Arzheimer, 2015) and sufficient numbers among the population seem amenable to appeals of such parties (e.g. anti-immigration sentiments - Bornschier, 2010; Kriesi et al., 2008), at least among those with lesser educational qualifications (Decker et al., 2012).

The reasons for this failure to succeed on a national level are likely tied to the German context, since Radical Right-wing parties seem to be a permanent mainstay of political systems across Western Europe since the 1980s (Van der Brug, Fennema & Tillie, 2000). First among them is the low appeal among the mainstream of openly racist, xenophobic or even nationalistic ideas in the public discourse (Goerres, Spies & Kumlin, 2018) and the accompanying stigmatization of such ideas by the media and political elite (Decker & Miliopoulos, 2007). Secondly, legal requirements stemming from the Party Law (e.g. minimum number of party members and participation in all 16 states to be eligible at the national level) limit the probability of entering the Bundestag for any smaller or younger party (Berbair, Lewandowsky & Siri, 2015) and finally, internal division within the radical right has been an impediment in their success (Bornschier, 2012).

We were interested to explore the, literally, extraordinary success of AfD in 2017 overcoming the hurdles of both political system and elite, mainstream parties. We use data generated through a Voting Advice Application to examine individual-level factors contributing to this success, splitting them into structural socio-demographic characteristics (e.g. sex), broader ideological placements (e.g. Left-Right)

and attitudinal preferences for specific policies. We focus our attention specifically to the ability of AfD to attract voters from the more mainstream and powerful parties, a relatively understudied niche in the literature studying individual level motivations for voting for radical Right-wing party voting (Coffe & van den Berg, 2016).

AfD a primer

AfD was formed in the shadow of the Euro debt crisis in February 2013, only 7 months prior to the federal election by former CDU/CSU members. Remarkably, by May the party had managed to establish branches in all 16 states (Berbair, Lewandowsky & Siri, 2015) and attract more than 10 thousand members (Arzheimer, 2015), becoming eligible for the federal election of 2013. With a relatively short party programme heavily focused on a single issue (Berning, 2017), standing against Germany-supported bailouts of banks and other European member-states (Arzheimer 2015; Berbair et al. 2015; Schmitt-Beck 2014) the party managed to gain traction due to its organisational capacities and media attention to its leader, B. Lucke (Berbair et al., 2015) ultimately achieving 4.7% of the popular vote, falling short of the 5% threshold.

With the European Parliamentary elections following closely, the party attempted to enhance its programmatic profile adding some nationalistic overtones and expanding on its support for market liberalism, in addition to adopting a more “soft” eurosceptic stance, opposing the current form of the Eurozone without explicitly advocating for a return to national currencies. Arzheimer’s comprehensive analysis of the party manifesto for the EP elections of 2014 placed the party to the right of the political spectrum, although not significantly more so than CSU¹ (2015) and the party managed to secure 7.1% of the vote and 7 seats in the European Parliament.

Internal contests followed, brought about by attempts to dissolve the party’s programmatic ambiguity and shed the single-issue party label, disagreements over EP group membership and connections to the anti-Islam PEGIDA movement. It appeared that one faction within AfD was intend on euroscepticism and the adoption of liberal market reforms while a second attempted to switch focus toward anti-immigration policies and rhetoric (Berbair et al. 2015; Franzmann 2016a; Lewandowsky 2015). This general shift to the Right and ensuing strife culminated in an unusually tense party convention, where the party’s founder Lucke lost his position from a constituency that considered “uncontrolled immigration”, rather than the “Euro crisis” the country’s main concern. (Schmitt-Beck, 2017). Lucke abandoned AfD to form yet a new party (ALFA, shortly renamed to Liberal-Conservative Reformers), with most of AfD’s representatives in the EU parliament and a number of officials following him (Berning, 2017), while other liberal elements within the party became more marginalised (Giebler and Regel 2017: 23).

¹ CSU is a party in permanent coalition with CDU and is not in electoral competition with CDU. It is generally more conservative and to the right of CDU on the political spectrum.

AfD continued its rightward shift with its “Herbstoffensive 2015” (Fall Offensive 2015) hosting rallies and events effectively mobilising support on the basis of opposing the grand coalition government’s immigration and asylum policies (Hambauer and Mays 2018: 150). Under its new national-conservative agenda, the party achieved even more electoral success at the State level, ultimately achieving to enter 14 of the 16 state parliaments, with vote shares ranging between 5.5% and 24.3% (see Franzmann, 2016; Schmitt-Beck, 2017). The particular configuration of anti-immigration rhetoric, euroscepticism and market-friendly policies is reminiscent of Radical Right-wing Parties (RRPs) elsewhere in the continent and in attempting to explain AfD’s success, it’s worth consulting the literature on this “family” of parties.

Radical-Right Parties in Europe

Although there is disagreement when it comes to the nomenclature (“radical right-wing parties”, “radical right-wing populist parties”, “niche parties” etc. see Hobolt & Tilley, 2016) and even sometimes their programmatic content and particular appeal for their respective electorates (Rodujin, 2018), there is remarkable agreement as to which parties belong in this “party family”. In the words of Mudde (2007; p.7), “we seem to know who they are even though we do not exactly know what they are”.

A successfully minimalist definition suggests two elements unifying a wide array of parties: First, adherence to an exclusionary ethno-cultural notion of citizenship (Immerzeel et al., 2015), which translates into some form of nativism (“non-native” elements are a threat to the nation state which should be as homogeneous as possible). Secondly some, at least, authoritarian tendencies, i.e. preference for a strictly ordered society and strong leadership, with more limited tolerance to pluralism and minority rights (Mudde, 2007; p.19-25). Additionally, a subgroup within the party family also subscribes to populist ideas, adopting narratives suggesting two homogeneous groups (“people” / “elites”) in an antagonistic relationship, whereby the virtuous former are set against the corrupt or indifferent latter, in a competition more “moral” rather than socio-economic or socio-cultural in nature (Mudde & Kaltwasser, 2013). Although the success of these parties to set national policy in the desired direction is debatable, even for immigration issues (Akkerman, 2012 cf. Zaslove, 2008, for other policy topics: see Bale et al., 2010; Immerzeel et al., 2015), their capacity to disrupt the political system promoting inter and intra-party conflict in response to their campaigns (e.g. Webb & Bale 2014 for the case of UKIP in the UK) is well-accepted, as is the magnitude of their electoral successes (Kitschfeld, 2007; van der Brug & Fennema, 2007).

The proliferation of these RRP has been largely enabled by the de-alignment between voters and parties observable in many Western industrialized nations (e.g. Bartolini and Mair, 1990; Dalton and Wattenberg, 2000) as well as the decline of the importance of traditional institutional cleavage (e.g. class), particularly for younger voters (see Walczak et al., 2012). For the case of Germany, as an example, Weßels notes that the share of voters without party attachment has doubled since 1976 (2014; p.239). As loyalties toward established parties, assumed to be acquired early in life and maintained through the lifespan (Rattinger & Wiegand, 2014; p.290) and primarily on the basis of social class become weaker, other decision-making processes become available, e.g. “issue” (Dalton 2000; p.25; Weßels 2014; p.240)

or “cultural” voting (Rydgren, 2012; Van der Brug and Van Spanje, 2009) – see below. In addition, a strong anti-establishment sentiment has developed since the worldwide financial crisis of 2008-2009 among the electorates, magnifying the anti-incumbency effect, with an increasing number of parties previously in power losing substantial vote share in subsequent elections (Hobolt & de Vries, 2015; Kriesi and Pappas, 2015; for Germany see Lohman, Brady, and Rivers 1997; Kedar 2004), driving voters toward formerly minor or marginalised parties.

Noting the increasing de-alignment between voters and parties and a generalised anti-establishment sentiment do not sufficiently explain the variability of electoral success of RRP across Europe or why such processes have not translated to electoral gains for the Left (with the notable exceptions of Podemos in Spain and SYRIZA in Greece). Attempts at explanations generally follow one of two complementary approaches (see Rydgren, 2007; Mudde, 2007; Van der Brug and Fennema, 2007), focusing on either constraints and opportunities offered by the political system in which parties operate (“supply-side” explanations) or on grievances on the part of the electorate (“demand-side” explanations).

Supply-side explanations

Supply-side factors contributing to the success of these parties are generally split into internal, i.e. under the control of the party itself (e.g. its organisational characteristics [Art, 2011] and external, for example institutional frameworks or treatment by the media (e.g. Muis & Immerzeel, 2016). Likely the most often studied aspect for the former category is the effect of strong or charismatic party leadership, suggesting that personified assessment of party candidates can replace party identification (e.g. Dalton and Wattenberg, 2000) as a vote-driver. More recent work however has raised doubts concerning the importance of leader evaluation for voters in general (e.g. Dalton, 2008; cf. Van der Brug and Mughan, 2007) and even in cases where positive leader evaluation turn out to be an important predictor of RRP voting, it proved to also be important for mainstream parties as well (e.g. Schumacher and Rooduijn, 2013).

On the external side, a particularly important roadblock for RRP (or any new party) have been institutional frameworks, such as majoritarian electoral systems (John & Margetts, 2009) and other rules, which tend to dissuade voters from preferring minor parties if, e.g. they are perceived as likely to not overcome the election threshold for entering Parliament (Givens, 2005). Another, often underappreciated external supply-side factor is the behaviour of established parties, since it is their positions that define the space in which minor or newer parties can inhabit (Koopmans et al., 2005; Arzheimer, 2009; Lubbers et al., 2002). Particularly relevant for the study of RRP are cases where major established parties converge toward each others’ ideological positions, allowing for a gap on the Right which radical new parties have been known to capitalize on (Norris, 2005; Arzheimer and Carter, 2006; Carter, 2005; but see Veugelers and Magnan, 2005). This became particularly obvious since the refugee crisis of 2015, with anti-immigrant policy advocacy uniting all successful RRP in Europe (Ivarsflaten, 2008; van Heerden et al. 2013).

Demand-side explanations

Most explanations utilising individual level data to explain RRP's electoral success are based on some form of the "losers of globalization (or modernization)" thesis, already existing since the 1960s (Mudde, 2010). This explanatory framework posits that globalization processes and changes in the labour market are leaving an increasing number of low-skilled or under-educated individuals vulnerable to economic deprivation (or fears of it), which eroded the political systems' representation function in Western Europe (Kriesi, 2014; p.364-365); this lowering of responsiveness on the part of established parties tends to enhance populist discontent and drive support for RRP's (Spruyt, Keppens & Droogen-Broeck, 2016).

In their simplest form, such explanations focus singularly on structural socio-economic elements such as class, sex, education etc., since it is precisely these that differentiate those susceptible to economic hardship. These groups of individuals threatened by rapid social change are postulated to vote in a reactionary manner, out of some general discontent (Betz, 1998) or purely for protest, thus being drawn to RRP's in an attempt to shock both mainstream and the elites (van der Eijk, Franklin & Marsh, 1996).

There indeed does seem to be a particular profile for RRP voters, who are more likely to be men, less educated (though only moderately so) and more often come from lower social classes (Arzheimer 2009; Rydgren, 2008; Van der Brug et al., 2000). Ultimately, however, this line of inquiry is unlikely to fully explain the RRP phenomenon (Betz, 2002). First, recent meta-analyses find that socio-structural information tend to explain only about 10% of variance in the success of RRP's (Bornschier and Kriesi 2012; Dolezal 2010). Similarly absent are often findings of an effect of political dissatisfaction on RRP voting (Arzheimer, 2008) and sometimes a negative correlation between discontent and support for RRP's is observed (Norris, 2005; p.183; Zhirkov, 2014). Moreover, as Norris points out such explanations cannot account for the uneven success of RRP's in countries at similar levels of modernization (2005; p.5).

More nuanced explanations suggest that support for RRP is a rational choice reflective of people voting on the basis of economic competition, preferring economic policies that protect them from potential economic hardship. Such explanations generally stem from the observation of an uneasy coalition within RRP constituencies between low-skilled workers and petit bourgeoisie elements (e.g. small-business owners) (Kitschelt & McGann 1995; Lubbers 2001), groups that do not correspond to traditional social structures (Ivaresflaten, 2005).

While reasonable, given that RRP support is higher among those more at risk or in fear of economic hardship (Lubbers et al. 2002; Rydgren 2004), such explanations fail to account for both the greater electoral success of today's RRP's compared to those of the 1990s (Mudde, 2013) and for the wildly different economic policies supported by these parties across Europe, from the social state policies and trade protectionism of Front National to the economic liberalism of UKIP or FPÖ in Austria (Kim, 2018). Additionally, Ivaresflaten (2005) has shown that the working-class and petty-bourgeoisie constituencies of RRP's are divided over their preferences for particular economic policies, although they share preferences over non-economic issues (e.g. anti-immigration and anti-EU stances); in fact, a number of researchers have suggested that RRP's in recognition of this fact attempt to mobilise across social or cultural values (Rovny, 2013; Röth et al., 2017). This should not be taken to imply that RRP voters are oblivious to the economic competition site, as they are often found to oppose redistributionist policies

(e.g. Zhirkov, 2014, Oeasch, 2008); however, they have also been shown to be driven by support for welfare policies, provided they are chauvinistic in nature (e.g. excluding non-citizens - Ennsner-Jedenastik 2016; Schumacher and Kersbergen 2016; Goerres, Spies & Kumlin, 2018 for AfD).

More recently, the “losers of globalization” framework has been expanded to include cultural competition (see Kriesi, 2014), reflecting the emergence of social values (e.g. tolerance) as an independent and equally important site of contention (see Inglehart, 1977; Inglehart & Welzel, 2005). This version of the thesis suggests that both cultural and demographic changes, as well as the increasing importance of supra-national organizations (e.g. the EU) are seen as a threat to traditional values and the homogeneity of national identity (Ivarsflaten, 2005; Van der Brug et al, 2005) fostering RRP success. Significant empirical support has been found for policy preferences of the socio-cultural variety, most notably anti-immigrant sentiment and euroscepticism represent the strongest predictors for RRP support in Western Europe (Lubbers and Scheepers, 2000; Lubbers et al., 2000; Eatwell, 1998). Explanations attributing RRP success to economic or cultural competition bring RRP into the mainstream of political competition, since their voters are suggested to be largely motivated by policy and pragmatic considerations (Zhirkov, 2014; Van Der Brug et al., 2005); in the words of Brug & Fennema: “Modern voters do not cast their votes in agreement with which social group they belong to, but in agreement with their own ideological and policy preferences” (2003; p.66).

Demand-side explanations for the success of AfD

Although we know a substantial amount concerning the AfD’s organization and official political agenda and discourse, we naturally know less concerning the voters of AfD, (Goerres, Spies & Kumlin, 2018), with only a small number of studies having the data to perform individual-level analyses at this point in time (Goerres, Spies & Kumlin, 2018; Berbuir et al. 2015; Schmitt-Beck 2014, 2017; Bermann et al., 2016; Schwarzbözl & Fatke, 2016). Notably, with the exception of Goerres et al., (2018) these analyses concern the federal elections of 2013 or EP elections of 2014, when AfD was not only more marginal (and thus less well-represented in surveys) but had not proceeded to its programmatic shift toward more standard RRP positions.

Studies employing data from the 2013 national and 2014 EU parliament elections generally find increased support for AfD among men, individuals with middle or high education and among high income groups (Giebler and Regel 2017; Bermann et al., 2016; cf. Schmitt-Beck, 2017 for education and income level). Accordingly, Schwarzbözl & Fatke, (2016) also report increased preference for right-wing economic policies and distrust toward the media, particularly when it comes to stories about asylum seekers (Schmitt-Beck et al., 2017). It should be noted however that concerning income, aggregate analyses at the State-level for 2013 and 2014, are, somewhat, in contrast, finding no evidence that AfD achieves higher gains in economically deprived (Schwander & Manow, 2017) or rural districts (Giebler and Regel 2017).

Similar findings are reported by Berbuir, Lewandowsky & Siri (2015) who used Bundeswahlkompas 2013 VAA data and found AfD voters to be generally younger, more educated and with higher incomes. Additionally, although they tended to place themselves on the centre of the political spectrum, they

tended to express anti-Euro and anti-EU sentiments and to favour authoritarian and anti-immigrant policies, although they were less strongly in favour of other socially conservative policies (e.g. restricting adoption to heterosexual couples).

Following the 2014 EP elections, there is evidence to suggest that AfD's constituency changed to be more in line with the profile of the typical Radical Right-wing party voter observed in Western Europe (Arzheimer and Berning, 2017; Goerres, Spies & Kumlin, 2018). Polling data since 2015, for example suggests a surge in approval rating among voters with lower educational qualifications (Brähler and Decker 2014; Brähler et al. 2016; Infratest dimap 2013-2017) and income levels (Infratest dimap 2013-2017; Niedermayer and Hofrichter, 2016). In the only available study employing multivariate analyses, Goerres, Spies & Kumlin (2018) find that men and individuals raised in Eastern Germany or abroad are more likely to vote for AfD, also reporting a marginally non-significant positive effect for medium-level education. As they note however, the predictive power of the model utilising socio-economic structural factors was limited; by contrast, the model's predictive capacity quintupled if they added anti-immigration attitudes, attitudes favoring the exclusion of non-citizens from welfare rights and measures of dissatisfaction with the government and political parties in general.

The context of the study – the 2017 German federal election

The public discourse in the run for the 2017 federal elections was dominated by the emergence of the immigration crisis, not unnaturally, given the large numbers of refugees entering Europe. Indeed, integration of refugees and asylum policies was reportedly either "important" or "very important" to them, with 47% considering it the most important political problem in the country (Infratest dimap 2017a; Infratest dimap 2017b). Commenting on a similar situation in 2009 Kurella and Pappi noted that parties failed to respond with policy positions in line with such concerns, rendering it nearly impossible for voters of Right-wing parties to "base their vote decision on the immigration issue, as there is no party representing their position" (Kurella and Pappi 2015: 99).

AfD on the other hand, realizing both the salience of the issue for the electorate, the heterogeneity of its pool of voter support and the threat of the party's own liberal market-oriented policy preferences to parts of its constituency (e.g. the unemployed – see Kim, 2018), actively attempted to mobilise along the lines of anti-immigration discourses (Geiges, 2018), more so in its rhetoric rather than in its campaign material (Franzmann, 2014; p.121-123). Combining successful issue ownership (Geiges 2018; p.66) and party responsiveness (see König 2017: 339), AfD managed to occupy the "gap" of the immigration issue (König 2017: 340) forming a constituency distinct from other parties focusing on xenophobic sentiment, anti-globalization and anti-EU positions (Siri, 2018; p.142). The attempt was indeed successful voters seeing immigration as a threat to the country being found to be 4,5 times more likely to vote for the party (Dilling 2018: 97) and the party's leader A. Gauland commenting that the refugee crisis noted that it was "a present for us [the AfD]" (Geiges 2018; p.52).

Contrast AfD's electoral strategy with strategic focus on a single set of highly salient issues with that of the incumbent parties CDU and SPD. The major coalition partner for the most part accurately predicted

that it would retain the Chancellorship (Wiliarty, 2018) and largely focused on promoting A. Merkel as an effective leader stressing the steady economic growth and low unemployment in the preceding period. Although it has been shown to be somewhat common for a centre-Right party in the presence of a radical competitor on its Right to attempt to regain ownership of the socio-cultural issue of the day (in this case immigration) by hardening its stance (Schain, 2006; van Spanje, 2010) this was less of an option for CDU given its incumbency, meaning it would have to do so against its own previous policy.

SPD on the other hand was faced with two commonplace problems, being a junior coalition partner and being a Social Democratic party. Kitschfeld (1999) described these parties' problems when it comes to forming an electoral strategy in terms of three dilemmas (economic, electoral and organizational) summarisable as the trade-off of attempting to appeal to some of its core constituencies and voters on the Left, risking alienating the more numerous centrist voters, as well as its putative position in a putative coalition government following the election. Indeed, SPD was in the difficult position of being part of a relatively successful coalition government, meaning that voters with primarily pragmatic concerns were more likely to vote for the major coalition partner, while voters on the Left were less likely to support a governing party. Simultaneously, being on the Left, it did not have easy access to the main point of contention between voters and government, the latter's immigration-friendly policies. As a result, the party attempted to focus on the electability of its newly elected leader M. Schultz, former speaker of the EU parliament who had not partaken in the incumbent government; following disappointing results in three state elections (including Schultz's home state), however, the party dropped in the polls and avoided polarising discourse which had the potential to increase the probability of a further term as a junior coalition partner, although voters ultimately were "unclear as to what the SPD stood for" (Turner, 2018).

The outcome justified the electoral strategy of AfD, which, with 12.6% of the popular vote became the third largest party in the 19th Bundestag. The two Volksparteien on the other hand saw record or near-record losses, barely managing to cumulatively gather 53.4% of the vote. AfD's electoral success is likely attributable to managing to benefit from CDU/CSU losses, particularly among middle-aged men (Neu & Pokorny, 2017; p.21) and mostly in Eastern Germany and Bavaria (Berning, 2017), although CDU/CSU very likely also bled support toward the more centrist FDP party. In addition, it seems likely that AfD cannibalised the constituencies of other far-right parties (Berning, 2017) and was particularly successful in mobilising previously disenfranchised voters (YouGov, 2017).

Research Hypotheses

Thus far, we provided a review of the trajectory of AfD from an, almost single-issue Eurosceptic party rationalising its positions on economic grounds to one whose main mobilisation efforts depend heavily on non-economic concerns, foremost immigration issues. We used the second section to describe the declining importance of traditional cleavages and the accompanying de-alignment between established parties and their constituencies and the ways that Radical Right-wing Parties across Europe have exploited the situation to introduce new topics and radical positions to the political discourse. The successes of these parties are attributable to their ability to mobilise previously disenfranchised or ineligible voters but primarily to attracting them away from the larger establishment parties. Recent

literature has suggested that explanations including voters' attitudes toward particular policies as predictors fare much better than explanations only employing structural socio-demographic characteristics, leading us to our first hypothesis:

H1: Individuals who voted for AfD in 2017, while having voted for either of the two more established parties (CDU & SPD) in 2013 will be primarily affected by affinity with the parties' policies rather than structural socio-economic variables (e.g. sex).

Moreover, RRP voters seems to be more readily mobilized by concerns relating to the socio-cultural rather than economic site of political competition and we predict that:

H2: Individuals who switched their vote to AfD will be more affected by agreement with party policies pertaining to the cultural axis of political competition and importantly by agreement with anti-immigration policies.

Method

All data employed in the analyses were obtained through ParteieNavi 2017, a Voting Advice Application (VAA) designed for the 2017 German federal elections. The VAA was in operation for the period 29th August – 23rd September, a day before the federal election of 2017, ultimately attracting 12580 users (a very modest number for the German context), primarily through a campaign using Facebook advertising.

VAA's are online platforms that provide information to their users regarding their closeness to political parties following their agreement or disagreement with a number of policy statements. The data were obtained in the usual VAA manner, with users freely visiting the website and responding in a self-completing capacity to a number of items, from demographics and political orientation questions, to placements of parties on e.g. the Left-Right axis and mainly 25 items concerning policy positions (e.g. "In the future, there should be a ban on diesel and petrol cars.").

Subjects

As is common in the case of VAA's (see Marschall, 2014) the tool yielded a dataset ($n = 12580$) highly non-representative of the German population in a number of different respects, the median user age being 36 years of age, predominately men (66.3%) and for the most part from West German States (80%) etc.

Data-preprocessing

After cleaning the data by eliminating users with unrealistically quick responses or other unusual responding patterns (e.g. straight-lining of responses) to the 25 policy preference questions (see Andreadis, 2014) we attempted to make the dataset more representative as to the German electorate.

We independently calculated two weights, one on the basis of a cross-tabulation of States (East/West Germany), age (into 4 age groups) and sex using census data² and a second on the basis of the election results of 2013. All weights calculated were satisfactory (<2.7), with the notable exception of females over 60 years of age in both East and West Germany, which were 8.9 and 8 respectively and were trimmed down to 4. The two weights were combined using a raking process using the anesrake R package (Pasek, 2018) yielding a dataset satisfactorily representative as to the characteristics employed (weighted n = 5425).

Stimuli

The main variables of interest here concerned users' vote in the previous election of 2013 and vote intention for the upcoming elections, with any user who did not declare either previous vote or vote intention for a specific party (e.g. "I am undecided") being eliminated from the analyses.

Independent variables

Wanting to focus on two aspects of voters' attitudinal characteristics, more broad ideological predispositions and narrower preference for particular cohorts of policies, calculating the relevant variables as follows:

a) self-placement on a Left-Right economic values axis: users were asked to place themselves and the six major German parties along a 0 (Left) : 10 (Right) continuum (see Appendix I for wording).

b) self-placement on a Progressive-Conservative social values axis: users were asked to place themselves and the six parties along a 0 (Progressive) : 10 (Conservative) axis. Users could skip either of the self-placement items altogether and approximately a third of them did so for at least one item.

Models 4-6, focusing on voters who switched votes from the two Volksparteien toward AfD, presented below, involved the calculation of the "distance" between voter and respective parties on these two axes. In both cases, ideological distance between voter and party was calculated as Absolute value {[user's placement of self] – [user's placement of party]}³.

c) Policy preferences: Users were provided with 25 policy statements toward which they could express their approval or disapproval using a 5-point Likert-type scale (Completely Agree : Completely Disagree). Although users were not allowed to skip any of these items, an explicit "No Opinion" response option was offered.

Although the user was asked 25 questions concerning different and independent policies, a number of different items were both thematically close and scalable into smaller (or larger) dimensions. Ultimately interested at examining the effect of highly specific groups of policies,

² <https://www-genesis.destatis.de/>

³ Note that for the case of users from the State of Bavaria, distance from CSU, rather than CDU was calculated, since the party does not stand in the State; subsequently, the distances from the two parties were merged.

we employed Mokken Scale analysis for polytomous items (Molenaar, 1991; Van der Ark, 2007 for the relevant R package) uncovering 8 small subscales of 2-4 policy items each (see Appendix I) pertaining to: Green policies, State intervention in the economy, Immigration, Tax & spending, EU matters, Socio-cultural values more broadly (e.g. “same-sex couples should not have full rights to adoption”) and state control (e.g. “Video surveillance of public spaces should be expanded.”). These small subscales (see Appendix II) remained stable across the raw and (more) representative datasets as to demographics and previous vote.

For each of the subscales we calculated the relevant scores (for models 1-3) by simply averaging users’ responses, after the items had been accordingly reversed, if necessary. For models 4-6, where again what was of interest was the interaction between the policy preferences of the users and the parties, an “agreement” index was calculated (-1 : +1) using the “hybrid” algorithm (see Mendez, 2014) for each of the 25 items independently, ultimately summing agreement indexes for each of the policy subscales. Parties were assigned positions using an expert survey employing the “Delphi” method (Gemenis, 2015). Items in which the three parties gave identical answers to were eliminated from this process.

Control variables

A number of demographic variables were of interest both in terms of theory testing (models 1-3) and as controls (models 4-6) and were the following: age, sex, education (operationalized as having a university degree or not), State (operationalized as East/West Germany) and interest in politics (trichotomised into low or no interest in politics, medium and fairly or very high interest in politics).

Results

We begin the presentation of our results by examining the trade-off of votes between the six main German parties. First concerning AfD, the party largely managed to retain voters who cast their vote for it in 2013 (85.3%) suggesting the formation of a core constituency for a (relatively) young organisation. Note however, that we find this result not to be unique for AfD, with the voters other non-Volksparteien (CDU & SPD) also remaining loyal to their party, perhaps an effect of our sample consisting uniquely of VAA users, given the latter’s high political interest. Considering defection from other parties toward AfD (Figure 1), we find that the party benefited greatly from the losses of CDU/CSU, in line with data from exit polls (Neu & Pokorny 2017; p.21), 63.5% of recent AfD voters originating from CDU/CSU. Contra previous evidence however (see Dilling, 2016), we find that AfD gained little support from SPD or parties to the latter’s Left.

Figure 1. Percentage of AfD supporters having voted for a different party in 2013

Regarding the two mainstream parties now, we find that they a substantial amount of their support leaked toward other parties with only 45.2% of users and 47.1% of CDU and SPD voters remaining loyal respectively, somewhat in line with the outcome of the elections, although this finding is likely greatly exaggerated. For the most part the majority of voters that abandoned the parties since 2013 moved to the extreme of each party's respective position. We found that 44% of CDU/CSU defectors switched to AfD and 54% of SPD defectors moved toward parties on its Left (the Greens and die Linke grouped together here), with little evidence for cross-block voting, although a large number of defectors moved toward the more centrist FDP party.

Figure 2. Percentage of mainstream party voters switching to any different party in 2017

Although tangential to the main focus of the paper, wanting to add to the literature concerning the characteristics of AfD voters in general, we decided to include a logistic regression predicting vote for AfD against voting for any other party. Table 1 presents three hierarchical models, the first only including structural socio-demographics, the second including the broader ideological self-placements and the third introducing policy preferences grouped thematically into seven categories (see Method section above).

Briefly commenting on these results, the primary observation is that the model only containing socio-demographics only offered little predictive power, which substantially increased when including policy preferences, in agreement with recent work on Radical Right—wing parties (e.g. van der Brug et al., 2007) and the findings of Goerres et al. (2018) for AfD in particular. At the lower level of analysis, focusing only on model 3, we find that the likelihood of voting for AfD increases when the user was a man (O.R. = 1.8), almost doubles when voting in Eastern Germany (O.R. = 1.97) and somewhat interestingly and in contrast to the findings of Goerres et al., also increases if the user had a university degree (O.R. = 1.5). We obtain no effect for age or interest in politics. Considering the ideological self-placements of AfD voters, we find no effect for self-placement along the Left-Right economic competition dimension but a significant effect for self-placement along the socio-cultural axis, with the probability of voting for AfD increasing as the user placed themselves closer to the Conservative end of the scale in line with previous findings for AfD (Berbuir et al., 2015) and RRP in general.

By far the most important predictors however proved to be policy preferences, in particular concerning immigration and EU matters in line with what could be predicted for both AfD and RRP in general, with strong anti-immigrant and anti-European integration and expansion being strongly correlated with voting for AfD. We also obtained a significant aversion among AfD voters toward state intervention directly promoting Green initiatives for expanding reliance on renewable resources. Also somewhat expected were the finding concerning the two policies we grouped under the name “social values”, limiting adoption rights to heterosexual couples and adopting Christian values as the guiding principle of German politics, two more traditional conservative issues, with disagreement in the adoption of these policies decreasing the probability of a vote for AfD.

-Table 1 about here-

Moving on to the main part of our analyses, we were interested in examining attitude-based motivations for switching one’s vote from an established and mainstream party toward a party largely considered on the radical Right. Thus, for the analyses that follow we excluded anyone who did not vote for either CDU/CSU or SPD in the 2013 elections and anyone who did not declare vote intention for the two parties or AfD in the 2017 election. As such, within this group of CDU or SPD 2013 voters, two subgroups are identifiable, those who remained loyal to their respective party (non-switchers) and those who defected to AfD in 2017 (switchers).

The most straightforward way to identify characteristics that favour switching would be to directly compare them (i.e. predicting AfD vote within this group of users) and attribute any differences found (quite reasonably) to some action of the party . This analytical process however, treats voting behaviour

as an attribute uniquely of the individual rather than of the individual and the specificities of the electoral context they are faced with; no differentiation is being made for example between two CDU voters, one of whom would never consider voting for AfD and one who was tempted to do so. The only way to achieve this differentiation is to include information from the parties themselves and thus we calculated distances from each party (for this model only CDU/SPD and AfD) on the two ideological axes and affinity with the parties' policy preferences.

Essentially then, our dataset contained some variables that are dependent only on each user (e.g. sex, age – choice independent) and some variables whose calculation takes into account the different parties' position (choice-dependent variables). This particular data structure lends itself to the employment of McFadden's discrete choice modelling technique (also conditional logit model). In this particular configuration of the logistic regression, each individual is treated as a number of "versions of themselves" as many as there are choices. In other words, each of the users in the data was assigned two rows, each of which contained the variables that were party-independent (e.g. sex) and respective variables that were party- (choice-dependent), e.g. one row containing the ideological disagreement score with CDU or SPD (depending on who they voted for) and another containing the disagreement score with AfD. Calculation of regression coefficients is made within-subject, so that what is being compared is each individual to their counter-factual counterpart, a second advantage of this method compared to e.g. multinomial regressions where some party has to be set as the reference/comparison category. We should note here that we consider that the model we employ here predicts "switching behaviour", although technically speaking the conditional logit model predicts "voting behaviour" (for any party), simply because we only include users who declared previous vote for either CDU or SPD, which were grouped together into a "mainstream" parties group; thus calculation of coefficients is made by predicting vote (AfD, since "mainstream" is the reference category), which is exactly the switchers group of interest here.

The first noteworthy observation is the rapid improvement of the model's predictive capacity upon addition of the ideological distance and policy affinity regressors and it appears that the voting behaviour of this particular subgroup was less dependent on structural socio-economic characteristics. Age was the only statistically significant predictor that correlated with vote-choice, with older users in our sample being less likely to defect to AfD.

-Table 2 about here-

Perceived distance between voter and party was a significant predictor with larger perceived distances on the socio-cultural axis making it less likely for a person to vote for the "offending party". As when examining all AfD voters, it appeared to be a significant concern for deciding one's vote, with more perceived distance decreasing the probability of casting that particular vote (here defecting to AfD from a mainstream party) but became non-significant after controlling for the effect of policy-related concerns. Minimally for the socio-cultural axis then, these findings are more in line with Proximity models of voting (e.g. Blais, 2001) which suggest that voters prefer parties that are ideologically similar, rather than the directional model (e.g. Macdonald, Rabinowitz, and Listhaug 2001) that contents that

voters like to vote more for parties that are ideologically in the same direction but who are more extreme.

Examining the effect of affinity to policy positions, as could be expected, higher affinity with AfD's positions tended to increase the likelihood of defection, except interestingly in the case of policies entailing state intervention in the economy, albeit to a statistically non-significant degree. However the "ability" to subvert voters was not equally distributed across the 7 sub-scales we employed. Affinity with a party's state interventionist, "pro-state control" or "social values" did not significantly alter the probability of voting for AfD. For the case of Green policies a trend for these policies affecting one's vote was present although to a marginally non-significant extend. On the other hand agreement with the party's positions strongly favoured voting for the same party in 2017, while disagreement drove voters to AfD (the strongest effect observed), showing the potential effectiveness of engaging in anti-immigrant discourses for radical Right parties (van der Brug et al., 2000). The second in order of magnitude effect was disagreement with the party on matters of furthering the European integration project, again a predictable result, given that Euroscepticism has been a traditional discursive locus for mobilisation of supporters of radical Right parties. In the case of Germany in particular the issue might hold promise for further success for actors on the fringe, given that the political elite, almost unequivocally considers the EU "as a good thing" (Kropp 2010; p140). Finally, we find that agreement with AfD's anti-income distributionist / anti-welfare positions led to switching from the two established parties in favour of AfD. This was somewhat surprising since the questions chosen were related to class-based income redistribution (e.g. "Top earners should be taxed more"), providing limited room for chauvinist-type welfare policies which are known to drive radical Right-wing parties' support in other contexts (Eger & Valdez, 2015 – Mudde, 2000).

Conclusions

In this paper, we took advantage of the dataset generated by the *ParteienNavi2017* VAA to examine attitudinal determinants of vote switching from the two mainstream parties in Germany toward AfD, whose trajectory went from a Eurosceptic and market-liberalisation oriented party to one that can be said to belong to the radical Right-wing party family. These parties, commonplace among Western European democracies have been found to be moving more readily along the socio-cultural, rather than economic political dimension (Kitschelt & McGann, 1995; van der Brug et al., 2005).

In line with the literature we indeed find motivations related to voting for AfD, whether switching is involved or not, to be connected to self-placement on the Progressive-Conservative axis and preferences for anti-immigrant policies more than to socio-demographic characteristics. It should be noted however, that although immigration is a main concern, AfD voters in our sample do not rely singularly on anti-immigrant sentiment to cast their vote and support for eurosceptic and anti-distributionist policies is also associated with switching one's vote to the AfD.

This being said, the study presented here suffers from a series of drawbacks, most of which are methodological in nature and should be taken into account when interpreting these findings. The

primary of these is that our operationalisation of who switched their vote or not depends on a question requesting participants to recall their 2013 vote in a period right before the 2017 election. Prior research has shown that peoples' recollections of previous voting behaviour are error prone (e.g. Powers et al., 1978; van der Eijk and Niemöller, 1979), with responders tending to report their current rather than past party preference (Waldahl and Aardal, 2000). Moreover, all analyses reported here are based on data generated through a VAA, whose users we know to be qualitatively different from the population in a number of respects, most relevant here education and interest in politics, variables we have not adjusted our weights for. As such, although we weighted the sample to be representative to the population as to some demographics and as to previous vote, it is possible that our results are not generalizable to the German 2017 electorate.

Research on Left-wing radical parties has suggested that their support increases when the mainstream parties on the Left move to centrist positions (Kitschelt and McGann, 2005; Achterberg and Houtman, 2006) and Spies (2013) has shown that RRP's increase their electoral share in countries where the economic dimension of party competition has decreased in salience and polarization. This might be particularly pertinent in contexts with a tradition of coalition governments, where the vote share of mainstream parties increases the closer they are to the middle of the electorate's Left-Right distribution (Ezrow, 2005) and participation in government becomes a concern for the parties that tend to avoid polarization for this reason (Strøm & Muller, 1999). In such situations, mainstream parties have troubles mobilising around new issues or adopting more radical positions on existing ones, particularly in times of crises (Vries & Hobolt, 2015), creating an opportunity for parties on the fringe to gain support. If such is the case for post-2017 Germany, the future success of AfD is likely to depend on the actions of CDU/CSU; Christian-Democrat and centre-Right parties more generally have been shown to do better in elections when they respond to the immigration crisis by increasing their anti-immigration messaging since they are seen as better able to deliver on the issues (see Ivarsflaten, 2005; Bale, 2008; Bale et al., 2013) and it is possible that CDU/CSU gains back the voters they lost in 2017 in the following election cycle. CDU/CSU itself is, of course, aware of the fact that there is a strong movement among its members for more restrictive policies toward immigration (WerteUnion, 2018) and a move in a similar direction has been indicated by SPD as well, with the party's chairwoman, A. Nahles proposing that the party develops a "more realistic" strategy that is not "an imitation of the liberal migration policies of the Greens" (Welt Online, 2018).

While AfD's success might be dependent on the actions of the established parties, it is difficult to maintain that the representational gap that exists on the Conservative end of the socio-cultural axis, among voters wary of the rapid changes in society around them. We cannot establish causality in any meaningful way and it is plausible that AfD has had an impact on the electorate's views, shifting their position toward more anti-immigrant and authoritarian positions either by making issues more salient (Bale, 2003; Ivarsflaten, 2005) or by shifting the Overton window (Immerzeel, 2015; Ivarsflaten, 2005; Van der Brug, 2003). Given however that the party itself seems to have moved in reaction to its constituencies' positions taken during 2015 and empirical evidence from elsewhere in Europe (Bohman and Hjerm, 2016) and the Dutch and German cases in particular (Berning and Schlueter, 2016), we find it

more likely that a sense of threatened interest among the electorate precipitates rather than follows radical Right-wing voting.

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to acknowledge travel funding through the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework NOTRE project (H2020-TWINN-2015, Grant Agreement Number: 692058).

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Predictor		Model I		Model II		Model III	
		Wald test ¹ statistic	Odds Ratio	Wald test	Odds Ratio	Wald test	Odds Ratio
Socio-demographics	Sex 1:= Man	56.37, p <.001	2.38	50.13, p <.001	2.404	8.82, p= .003	1.81
	Age	15.25, p <.001	1.01	9.25, p= .002	1.012	2.65, p= .103	0.99
	State 1:= East Germany	51.6, p <.001	2.38	37.58, p <.001	2.275	10.94, p= .001	1.97
	Education 1:= Uni degree	8.87, p= 0.003	0.73	3.238, p= 0.072	0.81	4.94, p= .026	1.5
	Interest in politics Mid	0.75, p= 0.385	.89	2.15, p=0.14	0.815	0.97, p= .322	1.22
	Interst in politics High	19.23, p <.001	1.8	12.93, p <.001	1.706	3.62, p= .057	1.52
Ideology score (0 :	Ideology: Left / Right 10:= Right	-	-	11.19, p= 0.001	1.078	0.04, p= .838	0.99
	Ideology: Prog / Cons 10:= Conserv	-	-	240.41, p <.001	1.427	16.17, p <.001	1.14
Policy score (-2 : +2)	Policy Dim: Green 2:= Anti	-	-	-	-	21.21, p <.001	1.57
	Policy Dim: State intervention in economy 2:= Anti	-	-	-	-	2.18, p= .139	1.17
	Policy Dim: Immigration 2:= Anti	-	-	-	-	109.77, p <.001	4.47
	Policy Dim: Tax and spending 2:= Anti	-	-	-	-	0.01, p= .927	0.99
	Policy Dim: EU integration 2:= Anti	-	-	-	-	130.27, p <.001	4.38
	Policy Dim: Social values 2:= Conservative	-	-	-	-	5.07, p= .024	0.84
	Policy Dim: State control 2:= Anti	-	-	-	-	1.18, p= .276	1.09
-2 LL		2360		2011		990.7	
Nagerkele R-sq		.11		.29		.72	
¹ df are always 1							

Table 2. Conditional logit model predicting vote switching toward AfD from mainstream parties						
	Model IV		Model V		Model VI	
	coef. z-value	OR / ME	coef. z-value	OR / ME	coef. z-value	OR / ME
intercept	-6.4, p < .001	.007	-3.11, p = .002	0.15	0.04, p = .96	1.04
Age	2, p = .07	.008	-3.7, p < .001	0.03	-2.24, p = .02	0.008
Sex 1:= Man	3.02, p = .003	2.2	-9.7, p < .001	0.07	0.55, p = .58	0.96
State 1:= East Germany	3.9, p < .001	2.7	1.3, p = .19	1.01	1.62, p = .1	2.5
Education 1:= Uni degree	-1.7, p = .08	.99	0.8, p = .42	1.4	-1.93, p = .059	0.99
Interest in politics (Mid or High)	2.72, p = .007	1.4	2.07, p = .03	2.1	0.28, p = .77	1.09
Ideological distance from party: Left / Right axis	-	-	-2.9, p = .002	0.99	-0.17, p = .86	0.002
Ideological distance from party: Progressive / Conservative axis	-	-	2.5, p = .01	1.7	-4.54, p < .001	0.009
Affinity with party's policies: Green	-	-	-	-	1.92, p = .055	-0.03
Affinity with party's policies: State intervention	-	-	-	-	-1.03, p = .301	0.001
Affinity with party's policies: Immigration	-	-	-	-	5.41, p < .001	-0.06
Affinity with party's policies: Tax and spending	-	-	-	-	4.17, p < .001	-0.05
Affinity with party's policies: EU	-	-	-	-	5.3, p < .001	-0.04
Affinity with party's policies: Social Values	-	-	-	-	1.7, p = .087	-0.05
Affinity with party's policies: State control	-	-	-	-	1.16, p = .243	-0.006
LogLik	-308.7		-165.8		-76.2	
McFadden R ²	.047		.487		.76	

Appendix I – Variables and operationalisation

Category	Variable	Measurement	Operationalisation
Voting behaviour	Previous vote (2013)	To which party did you give your second vote (party vote) in the previous Bundestag elections of 2013?	9 valid responses, including "Other"
	Vote Intention (2017)	Which party will you vote for with your second vote at the Bundestag election?	9 valid responses, including "Other"
Socio-demographics	Age	Year of birth:	NA
	Sex	Sex:	0:= man 1:= woman
	State	In which state are you eligible to vote?	0:= West Germany 1:= East Germany
	Education	What is the highest educational attainment you have obtained?	0:= without university degree 1:= university degree
	Interest in Politics	How interested are you in politics?	0:= Low 1:= Mid 2:= High
Ideological placement	Ideological self-placement: Left / Right	In politics it is often debated whether the state should intervene more or less in the economy. How would you place yourself and the following parties as to this? You can enter a value between 0 and 10 with the dials below. 0 means that the government should play an active role in the economy. 10 means that the government should not interfere with the market.	0:= Left 10:= Right
	Ideological self-placement: Progressive / Conservative	When people talk about politics, social issues are referred to as "progressive" and "conservative". Conservatives, for example tend to emphasise traditional values. Progressives are more open to alternative lifestyles. Where would you place yourself and the following parties? You can enter a value between 0 (progressive) and 10 (conservative) using the dials below	0:= Progressive 10:= Conservative

Appendix II – Policy items and scaling

Sub-scale	Question	Coef. H	Reversed?
Green policies	In the future, there should be a ban on diesel and petrol cars.	.648	No
	In the future, Germany should be completely supplied by renewable energy sources.	.648	No
Overall		.648	
State intervention	Companies should be allowed to set the amount of manager salaries without restriction from the State.	.336	No
	Job protection for companies should be relaxed, so that new jobs can be created more easily.	NA	NA ¹
	The State should take measures to enforce gender equality with regards to salaries.	.357	Yes
	There should be a general ban on the export of armaments by German companies.	.367	Yes
Overall		.353	
Immigration	Germany should continue to receive an indefinite amount of refugees from war zones.	.656	No
	Asylum seekers and applicants who have been rejected should be deported, including to Afghanistan.	.633	Yes
	There should be integration courses for all asylum seekers, even if there is a low chance of obtaining a leave to remain.	.598	No
Overall		.63	
Tax and spend	The property tax should be reintroduced.	.388	No
	Investments in social policy and infrastructure should take precedence over debt reduction.	.388	No
	Top earners ought to be taxed with higher rates.	NA	NA ¹
Overall		.388	
EU integration	German membership in the European Union is a good thing.	.591	No
	EU-Turkey accession negotiations should be ended.	.449	Yes
	Economically weaker countries, e.g. Greece, should not be in the eurozone.	.537	Yes
Overall		.534	
"Social values"	Same-sex couples should not have full rights to adoption.	.409	No
	Christian values should be the guiding principle of German politics.	.409	No
Overall		.409	
"State control"	A monitoring programme for the Internet is necessary to combat terrorism.	.625	No
	Video surveillance of public spaces should be expanded.	.625	No
Overall		.625	

Non-scalable	Tax credits for families with children ought to be introduced in place of joint filling for taxes by married couples (Ehegattensplittings)
	Germany should be more independent from the US as to foreign policy.
	Germany should increase its military spending to meet the 2% target of NATO.
	The sanctions against Russia should be relaxed.
	Referendums should also be carried out at the federal level.
	If the UK does not grant freedom of movement for persons after Brexit, it should not have unlimited access to the EU internal market.
¹ Items in which the parties were assigned the same answers were removed prior to analyses	